

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Sayfullayeva Xabiba Yoqub qizi

CULTURALLY MARKEDNESS OF STYLISTIC DEVICES

 Universal
Impact Factor

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

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 zenodo

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

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